

THE IMPACT OF CLINICAL EXPOSURE ON PRECEPTEE'S PREPAREDNESS FOR INDEPENDENT PRACTICE

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Abstract

Background: Preceptorship is an important, short-term relationship between a newly graduated nurse called a preceptee and an experienced nurse called a preceptor. The preceptor works as a mentor, counselor, teacher, and role model with the preceptee.

Aim: The study aims to know about the nature and impact of preceptorship of those nurses who take part in preceptorship programs.

Material and method: A descriptive cross sectional study design was used, and data was collected through a self-administered questionnaire from 84 participants. A convenient sampling technique was used in this study.

Results: In demographic section, majority of participants were female with ages ranging from 24 to 29 years. 72% of participants completed their preceptorship while 28% did not and majority of the nurses reported that this is a good and effective program. The job satisfaction, clinical skills and confidence improved due to this program.

Conclusion: The preceptorship program is very beneficial in terms of job satisfaction, retention of nursing staff, improving skills and confidence

INTRODUCTION

Preparing newly graduated nurses for entry into practical life is a top priority for academic and healthcare organizations. It is a big challenge for all health care settings to engage newly graduated nurses in a new environment. To efficiently prepare competent entry-level practitioners, it is very important to understand the clinical agency's expectations. Most clinical health care settings utilize some form of a precepted orientation experience for new graduated nurses (Hickey, 2009).

The competency in nurses is developed by gaining experience over passage of time in combination with gaining theoretical knowledge and the ability to be insightful with a new environment. The new graduates who start working in acute care hospital settings will face fast-changing healthcare systems that are considered by an increasing number of patients with acute, chronic and complex comorbidities. This can lead to higher demand of nurses who are expected to provide holistic nursing

care that meets patients' complex and diverse needs in acute care hospital settings (Willman et al., 2022). Nursing care in complex patient conditions are dynamic interactions related to instability, inconsistency and uncertainty from the viewpoint of the patient and the Registered Nurses (RNs) with processes such as personal, statement and cognitive, psychosocial and ethical aspects interacting with each other causing uncertainty and unpredictability in a situation (Huber et al., 2021). To grip the nursing care in a complex patient circumstance successfully, RNs need professional experience, expertise, knowledge and clinical reasoning skills, as well as contextual prerequisites such as time resources and support through teamwork (Kentischer et al., 2018).

A positive and effective working environment will empower the nurses to establish basic and fundamental patient safety, and it is a basic concern of today's health with the development of knowledge, awareness and self-consciousness demands on health care facilities. It also increases as nurses are the main pillar and the major working force of this system. Population is increasing very fast and the shortage of nurses is also going the same way side by side and this shortage is due to the more challengeable situation, in order to deal with all these issues, organizations must provide work place empowerment which can be defined as "having the power to access the organizational factors within the work environment that enable the employee to get work done" (Davies et al., 2006).

Previous studies show that newly hired nurses experience stress and anxiety when entering new clinical settings. Nurses' working environments have a direct effect on patient safety outcomes by influencing positive and negative ways. Nurses in poor working environments are more stressed than nurses who are working in good working conditions. The change of newly graduated nurses from the academic environment to practical environment is a difficult process that brings mental and emotional pressures. Upon entering clinical practice, these professionals experience tensions ranging from difficulty in communication to ethical dilemmas and overwhelming workloads. Lack of satisfactory skills and guidance contribute to increased stress and

often to the onset of emotional exhaustion and burnout (Narbona-Gálvez et al., 2024).

The nurse-patient relationship is also defined by the nurse's work environment. Patient safety is a major concern in the healthcare system, as hospitals focus on achieving better patient safety outcomes. Nurses play a fundamental role in establishing and maintaining a culture of patient safety. An effective work environment is a foundational variable that helps any health care provider, whether they are nurses or others involved in developing these safety protocols. Nurses play a vital role in patient safety and care for the best outcome of concern. Nurses Work environment has different apprehensions and defined as "the organizational characteristics of a work setting that facilitate or constrain professional nursing practice (Lake, 2002).

Orientation programs for newly hired nurses providing designated preceptors for graduate nurses are used widely, but few studies support their success in supporting graduates to undertake staff nurse positions (Brasler, 1993).

Preceptorship is important for newly graduated nurses as they transition from a different environment of being a student to a practitioner, the working environment, but it can be stressful and new for the preceptors. With the current problem of nurse shortage, perceptions about preceptorship need to be explored more precisely. Preceptorship helps in building up NGNs' competence and confidence levels as they start their new working lives. Normally, nurses must perform various advanced skills in clinical environments as preceptees (Quek et al., 2019).

Different nurses from different backgrounds, experiences and health care systems need to be accommodated by the new employment organization, which could be similar to or totally unfamiliar to the health care system encountered previously. Additionally, when such nurses enter the workforce, they can experience stress and anxiety and/or an unexpected cultural shock (Leigh et al., 2005).

Preceptorship also improves the quality of nursing education and practice, thus helping to reduce nursing shortages, by promoting recruitment and staff retention (Harbottle, 2006).

There are three main terminologies that are used in this context which must be understood.

Preceptorship:

Preceptorship is an organized short-term, and structured clinical educational program whereby an experienced, skilled and competent senior staff nurse facilitates the incorporation of a newly hired nurse into her/his role and responsibilities in a new clinical setup. This incorporation of the new nurses into a practical environment was achieved via the initiation of a professional, supportive, one-to-one relationship between the preceptor (senior staff nurse) and the preceptee (newly hired experienced nurse) over a flexible and limited time frame.

Preceptor:

It is a more experienced and senior nurse who acts as a role model, guide, mentor, counsellor, teacher and resource person to assist and provide guidance and support to the newly hired nurse to adjust and adapt to the new clinical setting during the preceptorship period.

Preceptee:

It represents a newly hired less experienced nurse who needs to be familiar with the clinical area and learn the essential skills and procedures to practice independently and competently and provide the required quality of nursing care to patients.

Patient safety concerns have totally changed with the development of health care systems and increased demand for patient safety concerns. And it has now become essential to deal with all these high opportunities to develop a work empowering environment that begins a sense of patient safety so that mortality can be reduced, reduction in mediational or other operative error. The roles of Nurse in this context have already been studied in different angles but the need of hours and the main point is to know which thing is required to upgrading the patient safety measures that directly and indirectly affect the safety issues of patient.

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of preceptorship programs on newly hired nurses in relation to patient care. Basically, this examination is an alternative pattern as today's primary health concern is patient safety maintenance and upgrading

as nurses can play a vigorous role in this regard. If nurses are provided with work permission, that will further contribute to these phenomena. However, the present study in the contrast of nurse's work environment and patient safety outcome will improve information and understanding in this respect. It would also provide a learning paradigm for the future and the study for the future to deal with today's high request of patient safety concerns. Study will also provide a sense of different indicators regarding patient safety and factors that influence nurse work environment positively or negatively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous literature specifies that the transition from a fresh graduate nurse to a trainee staff nurse could be a stressful experience. The novice trainee nurse feels upset when they do not receive adequate support during this transition period (Kumaran & Carney, 2014).

A well-planned preceptorship program with senior nurses may meet the recognition needs by increasing their competence, confidence, and socialization in the clinical setting and help healthcare agencies reduce orientation costs when they hire members after the program. As the focus of the western world is quality enhancement, Nurses work environment is the main contributor in developing and maintaining patient safety issues. Patient safety outcomes are directly proportional to the nursing efforts and inputs. And these inputs promote behavior, preventive care, provision of quality care, and prevention of harm to the patient. Patient safety practices are the main responsibility and duty of the nursing staff. Patient safety practice is defined as "Those that reduce the risk of adverse events related to exposure to medical care across a range of diagnosis and conditions". Profession of different organizational patterns effects differently to the patient safety outcomes and the nursing work environmental factor is on the top priority (Aiken et al., 2009).

The main indicator that predicts patient safety outcome is mortality as per the working environment but there are many more indicators that are linked with nursing care like medication errors and patient fall (Van Bogaert et al., 2014).

According to the National Quality Forum (2004), these latterly described indicators are highly linked with nursing intervention. The working environment has a direct influence on employee practices. If it is good and suitable and has harmony with employee demands, then the work outcome will flourish regarding the patient and nurse working environment influence a lot. A nurse who works in a best suitable environment can offer her best in patient nursing care as well as patient safety measures with the full acceptance of responsibility while on the other hand if there exist any imbalance between working characteristics and nursing job requirements then that will not influence badly on the nursing job related interest but also the interest related to the patient that directly or indirectly affects patient nurse relationship, others patients nurse related issues and patient safety outcomes as well.

In contrast to the patient safety issues, nurses' work environment has its own different variables. Job security, handsome salary, performance appraisal, job relaxation, advancing opportunities, risk prevention strategies, structural empowerment, personal alliance, and provision of adequate support is among them. These are all the things that enhance nurses satisfaction that are directly linked to patient care quality. These are all variables that increase patient safety outcomes by empowering nurses' work environment. On the other hand, there are also some variables that reduce or increase the risk of patient safety outcomes that are excessive workload, high demands of organizations, inadequate staffing lack of resources and support and the nurse's dissatisfaction as well.

Preceptorship programs are an important phenomenon in nursing professions. It can be applied in the study setting as part of an orientation program. Moreover, previously it was mandatory that all newly graduated hired nurses had to attend the preceptorship program (Webb, 2011).

Psychological job relation perceptions are also considered a supportive variable. Structural conditions do not empower nurses' work effectiveness. Data analysis indicated several areas of weakness in new graduate nurses' clinical skills. This information can be used by academic nursing programs to revise clinical experiences to better

prepare graduates for entry into practice. Findings can also be utilized to assist healthcare institutions with designing orientation programs for new graduate nurses. Suggestions are provided to help train preceptors for their important role. It is essential, particularly in today's complex healthcare environment, that strategies be explored to facilitate success of the emerging nursing workforce (Schultz & Videbeck, 2009).

The relationship between nurses' work environment and the patient safety outcome are closely linked to good, positive and effective work environment effect positively patient safety outcomes by providing boosters to the nursing work environment. There are a lot of studies that describe that there is a strong relationship between nurses' work environment and patient safety outcomes. There are many different publishing on the patient safety outcomes as well as nurses work environment previously but all of them just put pressure and focused on the staffing (Spence Laschinger et al., 2009).

According to Cashin & Newman (2010) the connection between a mentor and mentee was described as a long-term process that takes place between a senior more experienced and knowledgeable leader (mentor) and a junior, less experienced staff member with a possible capability for leadership (mentee). The relationship in this situation is built on mutual respect and compatible personalities (Cashin & Newman, 2010).

The implementation of a preceptorship program for orienting and supporting a newly hired nurses into a large tertiary-care teaching hospital is not only suggested but also expected by both newly hired nurses and organizational bodies (Robinson & Griffiths, 2009). Standardization of the preceptorship program, advancement of preceptorship guidelines, preceptor selection and training and supportive services for preceptors and preceptees are necessary elements for effective operation of preceptorship programs in any healthcare setting (O'Malley et al., 2000).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design:

A descriptive cross sectional study design was used in this study. This study design is the most suitable for

the current study. cross-sectional study design is cost effective and takes less time. One of the advantages of quantitative research is that large amounts of information can be collected within a short period of time (Mohajan, 2020).

Study Duration:

The duration of study was six months after the approval of the proposal. During this period, we visited different hospitals of Peshawar district which is located in KPK Province.

Study setting:

This Study was conducted in different tertiary care hospitals in district Peshawar, KPK Province. The hospitals were selected randomly among all large tertiary care hospitals.

Sampling Technique: We used Convenient sampling method for our study. This method is simple and very convenient for us.

Target Population: The targeted population were the staff nurses of different tertiary care hospitals. All the nurses present on duty and willingness to collect data were included in this study.

Sample Size: The sample size for this study was 110 which was calculated from Solvin's method. We distributed 110 questionnaires among nurses but only 84 were returned. It means the response rate was 76%.

Data Collection (procedure): Data was collected through a self-administered (Modified) questionnaire from available nurses on duty. Before taking the data, written consent was taken from all the participants. Questionnaires consist of different sections including demographic section, and other general variable related to the study. Such as impact of preceptorship questions, participation in preceptorship program, confidence building etc.

questionnaire were designed in both English as well in Urdu for simple understanding.

Inclusion Criteria

We have included the following participants as our inclusion criteria.

- Those who are willing to participate in this study.
- Those who understand Urdu and English. language.
- All nursing graduates.
- Both male and female nursing staff.

Exclusion Criteria

- The exclusion criteria were,
- Those who were not willing for provision of data collection
- Those who were absent from duty

Data analysis:

The data was analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 26) and MS excel. Data were expressed as frequencies and percentages via table and graph/figure.

RESULTS

Data was analyzed through MS Excel and SPSS as descriptive statistics having graph, and table were made accordingly.

The response rate from the participants were 76% among which majority were female having ages ranging from 24 to 29 of years. Survey responses regarding a preceptorship program include demographic details (age, gender, experience), information on preceptorship participation, and perceptions of its impact on clinical skills, confidence, leadership, and job satisfaction.

Section A-Demographic Information

In section A of this study the results consist of Age of the participants, which includes 5 options. Among all 5-options majority having age 24-29 and the minimum participants belong to age group of 40 and above as shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Participants and their ages

The second part of this section was gender, male and female. 47 out of 84 were female participants while 37 were male.

Working experience: in this part mostly participants (33 respondents) having 5 years or more experience. 14 participants had 3-4 years of experience, 27

having 1-2 years while 10 participants had experience less than 1 year.

Working Department: In this part we asked about the area/department/ward where participants work. Among the below 14 departments, the majority (50) participants were working in Medical and Allied as well as in surgical and allied as 19 participants, as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Participants from various department

Department	Participants
Anesthesia	1
CCU	2
Emergency	1
Endoscopy department	1
Gynae and OBS	1
ICU	1
Medical and Allied	50
Neonatology	1
Teacher	1
Nursery	3
Nursing college	1
Peads ICU	1
Supervisor	1

Surgical and Allied	19
Total	84

Section-B Experience of Preceptorship.

Question: How would you rate the overall quality of the preceptorship program you received?

In this variable we have asked the participants about the quality of preceptorship program they have received. The majority have replied to positive response in which 29 replied as excellent and 50 as good.

Question 2: How long was your preceptorship period?

About the duration of preceptorship, mostly have done 1-3 months (31 participants), then less than 1 month (20 participants), followed by more than 6 months (19 participants), and 4-6 months (14 participants).

Question 3: Was your preceptor supportive and approachable?

In this variable majority (73) participants agreed and strongly agreed regarding the support from their preceptor while very fewer (4) participants replied negatively and 7 participants replied as neutral.

Question-4: Did your preceptor provide regular and constructive feedback?

In this question we asked about the feedback from preceptor toward preceptee. Mostly (43) participants replied as always, 17 participants replied frequently, while on other side 4 replied rarely and 18 replied sometimes

Question-5: How effective were the teaching methods used during your preceptorship?

This question was about the effectiveness of teaching during preceptorship, 49 participants responded that it was effective, 21 responded very effective, 9 responded neutral, 2 responded in effective while 3 were in fever of very ineffective.

Section C. Professional development and skills.

Question 1. To what extent did the preceptorship improve your clinical skills?

In this section the 1st question was about the improvement of skills, 58 participants replied as greatly improved their skills, 24 replied as somewhat improved, 2 participants replied negatively, 1 participant replied as no change.

Figure 2: Extent of skills Improvement

Question 2: To what extent did the preceptorship program help you build confidence in your nursing practice?

In this question mostly the participants replied that their confidence was built-up. 48 participants replied as greatly increase and 32 somewhat increase while a total of 2 participants replied in negative and 2 participants replied as neutral.

Question 3: Did the preceptorship program help you feel more prepared to work independently?

In this question, the researchers asked about working independently. 76 participants agreed and strongly agreed, and 3 participants disagreed and strongly disagreed while 5 were neutral about this statement.

Question 4: Did the preceptorship influence your decision to stay in the nursing profession?

In this question we have asked about the retention in Nursing profession, 75 nurses said that preceptorship positively influenced their decision to stay in nursing while the remaining 9 nurses were not replied positively.

Section D.

Question 1: How well did your preceptor help you manage stress and emotional challenges in your role?

This chart shows the results of stress and emotional challenges. Mostly participants (67) replied to positive feedback and 17 participants replied as neutral and poorly.

Question 2: Did the preceptorship help you develop positive working relationships with other healthcare professionals

Regarding positive relationship between health care professionals, 78 participants replied as agreed and strongly agree while 5 neutrals and 1 strongly disagree.

Question 3: How well did your preceptorship support your personal well-being (e.g., work life balance, mental health)?

36 participants responded very well, 33 well, 12 neutral and 3 poorly. It means mostly having a positive response.

Question 4: Has the preceptorship program had a positive impact on your job satisfaction? The impact of preceptorship on the job of a preceptee is very important. In this regard we have asked this question, and 33 participants responded strongly agreed and 45 agreed while 6 neutral.

Question 5: Do you feel that the preceptorship prepared you for leadership roles in the future?

Leadership roles are also important in learning during preceptorship. We asked from the participants whether the preceptor has prepared you for this leadership role or not. 78 participants replied yes, 4 replied No and 2 were not sure.

Question 6: Do you think the preceptorship program should be a mandatory part of nurse training?

In this last variable we have asked if you think that preceptorship program must be mandatory for nurses or not. Mostly (77) participants respond Yes, while 4 participants replied No and 3 were not sure about this.

DISCUSSION

This current descriptive study was focused on the impact of clinical exposure on preceptee. For newly joined graduate nurse has so many challenges in new clinical area, new environment, new staff members and cooperation from their colleagues. There are four sections including demographic. In each section we have asked some questions from participants regarding the preceptorship program. Participants include different age group people in which majority were 24-29 year of age and mostly female nurses.

Preceptorship programs are very beneficent for newly hired nurses. 61 out of 84 have completed the formal preceptorship program, and the remaining 23 were not done with this program. It is a need for time for all established organizations to provide preceptorship programs for newly hired nurses. Preceptorship helps in building up graduate nurses' competence and confidence levels as they start their work fresh (Kelly & McAllister, 2013).

According to Tremblay et al (2012) Successful preceptorship programs may contribute to increased job satisfaction and decreased turnovers. This is very

important for organizations to retain the nurses for a long period of time (Lavoie-Tremblay et al., 2012). In our study 50 participants replied that their program of preceptorship was good while 29 participants respond as excellent.

Personal features affected the working style of each preceptor and, invariably, the preceptorship experience they offered. Leadership style and the level of a preceptor's engagement can affect a preceptee's transition experience and job satisfaction. In this study the majority (73) participants were agree and strongly agree regarding the support given from their preceptor while very few number (4) participants were not agreed. There must be a positive and productive relationship between preceptee and preceptor.

Good communication and feedback are the important features in preceptorship programs. In the study of Bengtsson et al (2015) it is stated that good feedback is important in preceptorship as it relieves NGNs of uncertainties by building their confidence levels, which is a key objective of preceptorship (Bengtsson & Carlson, 2015). This current study resulted that they always received good feedback from their preceptor. Technology such as social media and mobile text messages played a part in linking the gap between preceptors and preceptees.

Leadership qualities must be seen by the preceptee in their preceptorship. A study suggested that the selection of preceptors should include an assessment of their leadership features as preceptors serve as role models to preceptees. Furthermore, a preceptor-preceptee relationship requires struggle to develop and maintain. Hence, even with the best planning by the nursing manager, reciprocal acknowledgment and respect are needed between the preceptor and the preceptee for their relationship (Lockwood-Rayermann, 2003).

The clinical skills must be buildup in the graduate nurse during this program. It's a golden opportunity to polish his/her skills and seek more practical and theoretical knowledge from their preceptor. In this current study 58 nurses (73%) said their skills greatly improved, while 24 (26%) noted somewhat improved during the period of preceptorship. Another study shows that the clinical practice of 53.9% of participants improved, and the preceptorship program helped them in the

transition period from student to a clinical nurse, while 53.9% described that the preceptorship helped them adjust to their new role in clinical training, and 46.7% reported that the preceptorship stimulated them in their future career roles. With greater self-confidence, there was a greater degree of perceived nursing competence in practical skills. Preceptorship enhanced learning and the overall perceived competency and confidence of the nursing students (Wieland et al., 2007). The result of our study also shows that 63% of nurses reported that their confidence increases while 32(42%) saw somewhat increased confidence.

The study was done in Taiwan which indicated that implementation of the effective preceptorship program decreased the turnover rate by \$186,102 during the first six-month periods and medication errors made by new nurse from 50% to 0%; and the incident rate of adverse events and falls (Porter-O'Grady, 2009).

CONCLUSION

Clinical preceptorship is one of the important tools for newly hired nurses in any organization such as hospital. This is all about just orientation but detailed training. Clinical areas for newly hired nurses will be a new environment for fresh nurses who have just graduated, and this is theory to clinical transition phase.

Clinical preceptorship provides a close environment for senior nurses to seek help from junior students with the opportunity to gain nursing knowledge, skills, attitudes and the fundamental framework necessary for carrying out the nursing processes. The preceptorship program is effective, with a high positive impact on practical skills, confidence, and job retention in clinical settings. Shorter preceptorships, which consisted of 1-3 months, were the most common but still provided significant benefits. Preceptorship may develop a leadership role among nurses which is a major benefit, with 95% of nurses feeling prepared for leadership roles.

From this result, the participants shared their experiences regarding seeking positive things from their senior like skills, positive feedback, practical knowledge, confidence, and working independently. The knowledge which the nurses have seek during

study as theoretical knowledge is now to be applicable in a practical setting.

The result of this study is almost good and positive. Every nurse must go through this training of preceptorship. The preceptorship program was very productive, and they seek more things from their seniors.

RECOMENDATION

As we know, preceptorship is very important for newly hired nurses. And the environment is also new for these nurses so this program will be more beneficial. It must be adopted by all government and private organizations. It is recommended that this program duration must be at least 3 months. It is a very productive orientation session for the long term. It is recommended to high authority and all health care organizations as well as those nurses who do not receive preceptorship they must be done for greater benefit. Preceptorship is more practical than theoretical.

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